

Customer Value: The Next Source for Competitive Advantage

Dr. Namratha

Faculty member, Dept. of Commerce, S.P & J.M Bohara, Commerce College SHORAPUR

Dist: Yadgir -Karnataka

Corresponding Author- Dr. Namratha

Abstract

On Driven by more demanding customers, global competition, and slow-growth economies and industries, many organizations search for new ways to achieve and retain a competitive advantage. Past attempts have largely looked internally within the organization for improvement, such as reflected by quality management, reengineering downsizing, and restructuring. The next major source for competitive advantage likely will come from more outward orientation toward customers, as indicated by the many calls for organizations to compete on superior customer value delivery. Although the reasons for these calls are sound, what are the implications for managing organizations in the next decade and beyond? This article addresses this question. It presents frameworks for thinking about customer value, customer value learning, and the related skills that managers will need to create and implement superior customer value strategies.

Introduction:

Global competition, and slow – growth economies and industries, many are on a journey, searching for new ways to achieve and retain competitive advantage. Nearly two decades ago, quality management became popular, and managers learned how to improve the quality of both their organization's products and internal operations processes. These efforts brought important performance improvements but, ironically, too often they reinforced an internal orientation. Most quality tools help managers make internal process and product improvements.

Managers have been implored to consider their customers when determining which improvements are need, and customer satisfaction measurement (CSM) has emerged to bring the "voice of the customer" into quality efforts. However, application of CSM has fallen short of its promise for several reasons. First, many organizations have responded by setting customer satisfaction goals and strategies, but only a few have rigorously measured their customers' satisfaction Second, even those companies that measure satisfaction may not act on the results If CSM is not backed up with in-depth learning about customer value and related problems that underlie their evaluations, it may not provide enough of the customer's voice to guide managers in how to respond.

Need of the study

One of the biggest problems facing senior managers today is how to attract customers and attain growth, often in an environment where products and prices among competitors are moving steadily closer together. Traditional bases for differentiation, such as product features or cost, are becoming less tangible. So senior management is forced to look for new ways to be attractive to a target market. Many companies now use the CVM approach to identify the "value" they can deliver,

not only with products but also through processes and services. These companies engineer their business capabilities to deliver "ideal" customer-defined value at each customer interaction.

Although necessary to compete in today's industries, quality may no longer provide a clear source of competitive advantage. More and more managers lament that product innovation and quality no longer provide the basis for a competitive edge. Some organizations have turned inward again by trying to improve performance through more encompassing structure and process changes. Downsizing, restructuring, and reengineering have emerged as popular management tools for creating "lean and mean" organizations. Unfortunately, experience is mixed as to whether these tools have delivered on their promise. The way organizations do work may change but still do not have the desired impact on bottom- line performance.

Quality improvements and organizational tinkering continue, but so do the external market-based pressures that gave rise to them. Consequently, the search for advantage goes on, and so it is important to ask where organizations will look next for sources of advantage. Instead of the same focus on internal processes and structure, the next major management transformation likely will come as organizations turn more of their attention outward to markets and customers. Consistent with this prediction, there are no shortages of calls for organizations to reorient strategy toward superior customer value delivery.

Objectives of the study

This article discusses operational capabilities for an organization wanting to improve at competing on superior customer value delivery.

1. To know what and how organizations should learn about customer value.
2. To know the translation process framework for bridging customer value learning, strategy

thinking about customers, and internal process management.

3. To discuss the implications of customer value for management practice, future customer value-related research, and the education of managers of the future.

The Concept of Customer Value

The term value shows up in several very different contexts. For example, an increasingly common perspective on managing organizations argues that creating and delivering superior customer value to high-value customers will increase the value of an organization. The latter two value concepts consider value from the perspective of an organization. High-value customers quantify the monetary worth of individual customers to the organization, whereas value of an organization quantifies an organization's worth to owners. Customer value, on the other hand, takes the perspective of an organization's customers, considering what they want and believe that they get from buying and using a seller's product. This section addresses this customer- directed concept.

Defining Customer Value

More often than not, commentaries on customer-oriented management practice provide only a vague sense of what customer value means. Fortunately, some of these commentaries recognize that making customer value strategies work begins with an actionable understanding of the concept itself. Yet even a cursory look at their definitions reveals a surprising diversity of meanings:

1. Value is the consumer's overall assessment of the utility of a product based on perceptions of what is received and what is given.
2. Value in business markets is the perceived worth in monetary units of the set of economic, technical, service and social benefits received by a customer firm in exchange for the price paid for a product, taking into consideration the available suppliers' offerings and prices.
3. Buyers' perceptions of value represent a tradeoff between the quality and benefits they

perceive in the product relative to the sacrifice they perceive by paying the price.

4. Customer value is market perceived quality adjusted for the relative price of your product.
5. By customer value, we mean the emotional bond established between a customer and a producer after the customer has used a salient product or service produced by that supplier and found the product to provide an added value.

The rows in Figure 1 concern what the customer's perception of value is about. Either prior to purchase or constructed later at the time of use, customers may imagine what value they want (i.e., desired value). Customers learn to think concretely about value in the form of preferred attributes, attribute performances, and consequences from using a product in a use situation. In addition, they form evaluative opinions or feelings about the actual value experience of using a product (i.e., received value). During the choice task, customers may predict received value, but during use they actually experience received value.

1. Although the above classification reveals important distinctions among types of customer value, the concept appears to take a much narrower perspective when applied in customer research. Operationally, value frequently is measured as attribute-based desires (or preferences) that influence purchase (upper-left cell of Figure For instance, focus group research is widely used by organizations to identify customers' attribute drivers or "key buying criteria," such as product quality and on-time delivery. Similarly, satisfaction research typically asks customers to evaluate the brand or seller on those attributes thought to influence customers' purchase decisions. We are likely to miss important nuances of customer value if we limit customer learning to this narrow point of view. For example, customers prefer dimensions of value other than just attributes, such as use consequence.

FIGURE 1
Classification of Customer Value Concepts

		Nature of information is ...	
		Snapshot	Longitudinal
Information describes...	Customer-determined performance	Short-term customer-focused performance information	Long-term customer-focused performance change information
	Performance causes	Information on determinants of short-term customer-focused performance	Information on determinants of long-term changes in customer-focused performance

Customer Value Concept as a Decision Tool

The concept of customer value becomes an important management tool only if and when it is shared within an organization. Those involved in creating and implementing customer value delivery strategies need a common framework for thinking about customer value. For example, an operational concept of value, such as the customer value hierarchy, helps to specify exactly what managers should learn about their customers. Most important, the hierarchy argues for looking beyond the so-called attribute-based key buying criteria. Sellers should learn about consequences in use situations that customers want (or want to avoid) and the goals to which those consequences lead. Ultimately, it is how customers see value that influences what they will do in the marketplace.

Organizational Barriers to Competing on Customer Value Delivery

Competing on superior customer value requires more than a set of customer value tools for managers; it also entails making major changes in the way organizations are managed. The question is whether an organization can make the needed changes. With regard to customer value, many organizations, perhaps unintentionally, erect barriers that keep them from shifting from an internal orientation to one that encourages competing on superior customer value delivery. To build customer value delivery capability often requires finding and overcoming organizational culture, procedural, and learning barriers. The initial challenge is to recognize that they exist.

Organizational culture barriers. The most difficult barriers to overcome are embedded in organizational culture, particularly the existing employee performance measurement and reward systems. Although managers may not acknowledge such barriers directly, they are reflected in objections that managers sometimes raise when asked to engage in more customer value learning (e.g., "I already know what my customers want, "I don't have time for all that research"). Such objections may indicate lack of rewards for customer value learning or lack of understanding of the link between customer learning and performance on those things that are rewarded.

Organizational procedural barriers. Every organization has accepted procedures in place with which managers are quite comfortable. Although some procedures may not foster competing on customer value delivery, they are used because of inertia (e.g., "that is how we do it around here") or preference (e.g., "I like to do it the way we always have"). For instance, most organizations attempt to identify what customers want. Some do it through brainstorming sessions where managers speculate about the value dimensions that customers desire.

Yet this approach ignores the fact that managers are not particularly good at using personal experience to surmise what their customers want.

Even organizations that rely on research to learn about customers may erect procedural barriers. They may over-rely on "favorite" techniques, such as focus groups, or follow reporting procedures that limit the communication of customer value information to managers who need it. For example, research staff often are asked to condense results into very short summary reports (e.g., the so-called one-page memo). Short reports may be good for some purposes, but not for communicating the complexity and richness of customer value findings coming from qualitative research. They also frustrate research staff who struggle to communicate all that has been discovered in such a short space. Ironically, those managers who insist on short reports are hurt most. They are likely to miss important findings, perpetuating their tendency to base decisions on oversimplified mental models of customers.

Managerial learning barriers. To compete on superior customer value strategies, an organization's managers must upgrade and acquire new skills. Learning becomes an issue when it does not keep pace with the stream of new knowledge being developed on the tools of customer value. Managers may be too committed to the "way we do things," too busy with other responsibilities, not adequately informed when new tools come along, or not convinced that using new tools is worth the effort. Part of the problem may be difficulty in overcoming the organization's culture, but another part may simply be the lack of periodic training in new tool developments.

Implications of customer value-based competition

In the new era of competing for superior customer value delivery, organizations inevitably will feel compelled to capabilities build customer value learning and translation. Many are already looking for help. Academia can respond by redirecting research toward improving and expanding the tools of customer value that are needed to help organizations make the transition as well as by rethinking the education of prospective managers.

Improving Customer Value Delivery Practice

Quality management convinced many organizations to become highly information driven in managing the operations side of the business. Competing on superior customer value delivery will place similar pressure on organizations to become equally information driven in the marketing side. As customer retention and customer relationship building and maintenance take on more priority, customer learning and translation processes become

a core competency issue. Competing on superior value delivery will force organizations to, in effect, compete on superior customer value learning and translation capabilities.

This transition will not be easy. Managers across an organization will have to learn how to use quite different kinds of data than that which drives quality initiatives. Even marketing and sales, which have experience with customer research, may have to work with a broader array of such data to enhance customer value learning. Many will need new information skills. Customer value-related data, in many respects, are softer (i.e., reflect customers' preferences and perceptions), less quantitative, and require a broader set of information tools than that which dominates current practice. In addition, CVOMIS improvements also may require more involvement by customer contact personnel in gathering data from customers. For example, salespersons may have to become more skilled interviewers and observers when working with customers to get real-time data on customer value.

Superior translation skills also can be an important source of competitive advantage. A critical issue here is the myth of the "key buying criteria" assumption made so frequently by managers, which says that relatively few key customer value dimensions drive customer behavior. Much of the basis for this assumption comes from the sales transaction perspective so prevalent among managers. If an organization limits its research to understanding what drives an individual purchase incident, there probably will be a few desired value dimensions on which sales transactions turn. However, we should not expect those value dimensions to remain the same over time. Strategically important value dimensions are likely to change across customer segments and over time. Further, as organizations shift more resources from acquiring customers to retaining customers, customer value dimensions that drive customers' commitment to seller relationships take on added importance. These dimensions are likely to be many rather than few. In short, the challenge for competing on customer value delivery is more likely to be one of translating customers' evaluations of received value on many desired value dimensions into responsive value delivery, rather than one of focusing on relatively few key buying criteria.

Implications for Future Research

Although the philosophy and persuasive arguments for organizations to compete on superior customer value delivery are well developed, the tools of customer value lag behind. Consequently, tremendous opportunity exists to improve on current tools and develop new ones. New research can help by developing (1) richer customer value theory, (2) more effective customer value methods tools, and

(3) more evidence of the impact of applying specific customer value tools on organizational performance.

Richer customer value theory. Organizations committed to customer value learning have to know what is most important to learn. Such choices are not easy because the possibilities are almost endless and the investment in information activities substantial. Theory about customer behavior provides one important tool for locking onto the critical things that managers need to know. Periodically, we should evaluate whether existing theory is adequate for guiding customer value learning in organizations. Much of this article argues that existing theory underlying current customer value and satisfaction learning by organizations is not. For example, current CSM practice is founded on discontinuation theory and multiattribute attitude theory largely developed in the 1960s and 1970s, which does not take advantage of newer customer value concepts.

We need richer customer value theory that delves deeply into the customer's world of product use in their situations. In part, this new theory should help us understand how customers form preferences that reflect desired value. Expanded theory should also explore the linkage between customers' preferences for desired value, evaluations of received value, and overall customer satisfaction feelings within the framework provided by the customer value hierarchy. For example, are these linkages the same at each level in the hierarchy? Such richer theory will have an important impact on what organizations will learn about customers in the future.

Equally important, we need new theory to describe how and why customers' desired value changes over time, from purchase to use or over multiple-use occasions. Are there predictable triggers that lead to customer value change? What happens during a value change process? What is the role of product offer components (e.g., new technology, products, salesperson interactions with customers) in causing change? When things go wrong in customers' use situations, what are the nature and causes of customers' tendency to devalue products over time. We have few answers to these kinds of questions, and (o organizations currently have limited ability to foresee customer value change coming. A theory of customer value change could be the cornerstone for developing processes and techniques for predicting that change and expanding the lead time for sellers to determine how to take advantage of opportunities created by that change.

Implications for Marketing Teaching and Learning

Education must play a role in helping organizations transition toward competing on

superior customer value delivery strategies. We should start by identifying critical managerial skills that organizations need to develop customer value-related capabilities. Only then can education organizations evaluate existing curricula and learning processes to identify improvement and innovation opportunities. For example, this article argues that customer value learning and translation skills are essential for organizations to compete on superior customer value delivery. To what extent do current marketing and business education programs effectively help students acquire these skills? How can we help students understand the importance of deep learning about customers, as well as want to learn specific customer value information and translation skills? How do we help students with different functional interests (e.g., operations vs. marketing vs. sales) develop skills needed to share customer value learning and interact cooperatively in managing internal processes that deliver the kinds of value customers desire? Only by answering these kinds of questions can we expect to see significant changes made to improve educational programs needed for supplying organizations with managers adept at competing on superior customer value delivery.

Conclusion

Every company in today's business environment is stressing customer focus. However, what's lacking in most companies are useful and practical ways to capture customer needs, measure how well you're satisfying those needs, and build actionable plans to improve your company's bottom line—that's what customer value management will do for your company. Competing for advantage in markets through superior customer value delivery is here to stay. There are too many long-term pressures on businesses to move in this direction to believe otherwise. Customer value-based competition represents the next major shift in managerial practice, complementing but, at the same time, moving beyond the quality management focus of the past two decades. This shift will not be incremental; rather, it will require a very different way of managing. It builds on the already excellent capabilities that many organizations have acquired for managing the quality of internal processes and products, but it also requires a different set of skills to marry internal quality with external customer value. A customer value orientation will mean rethinking organizational culture, structure, and managerial capabilities. Organizations need help to make the transition from a largely internal to a more balanced internal and external focus on customer value. Partnerships between business organizations and educational institutions will help advance knowledge and assist in increasing the pace at which that knowledge is diffused into organizations. These

partnerships already are happening, and they signal an exciting new era of cooperation between business education and organizational practice that should benefit both. Customers who experience more responsive sellers will benefit as well.

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